

CULTUROLOGY

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NIZAMI GANJAVI'S GHAZAL IN JAHANGIR JAHANGIROV'S CHORAL CREATIVITY

Abstract

The article examines the issues related to the embodiment of the lyrical poetry of the great Azerbaijani poet and thinker Nizami Ganjavi (1141–1209) in the choral works of the prominent Azerbaijani composer Jahangir Jahangirov. The study analyzes the composer's work *Ghazal for mixed choir and piano*, written to the poetic text of Nizami. The conducted research shows that this choral composition is characterized by its strong connection to national traditions and its lyrical qualities, and it opens broad horizons for the use of the ghazal genre in choral works. In Jahangirov's choral ghazal, the subtle lyricism of the music following the literary text, the unity of word and music, a firm connection with the musical heritage of his people, references to national modal systems and mugham sections, as well as vivid melodicism, are clearly manifested.

Keywords: Nizami Ganjavi, Jahangir Jahangirov, poetry, lyricism, ghazal, music, choral art

The outstanding representative of world literature, the great Azerbaijani poet and thinker Nizami Ganjavi (1141–1209), authored five widely acclaimed poems written in the masnavi form (*The Treasury of Secrets*, *Khosrow and Shirin*, *Layla and Majnun*, *Seven Beauties*, *Iskandarnameh*), as well as numerous lyrical poems. These works constitute an inexhaustible source of inspiration, poetic and moral values, imagery, and narrative plots for creative individuals. From *The Treasury of Secrets*, it becomes evident that when the philosopher-poet composed his first poem, he was already recognized as a lyric poet, and his ghazals were performed by singers.

Nizami's words are sweet, piquant, and witty; every ghazal is memorized by singers [4, p. 66].

It is well known that the ghazal is a lyrical poetic genre of classical Eastern poetry and is distinguished by its close connection with music. A ghazal typically consists of 5–10 couplets (each couplet comprising two lines) rhyming according to the scheme aa, ba, ca, da, etc. It is primarily devoted to the depiction of the beloved and the expression of the lover's emotions. In the first couplet, both lines rhyme, while in the subsequent couplets only the second line is rhymed. The poet's pen name is indicated in the final couplet, and each couplet generally conveys a complete idea.

The ghazal genre occupies an important place not only in Azerbaijani poetry but also in musical culture. Alongside the tradition of reciting ghazals to musical accompaniment and their function as poetic texts of vocal-instrumental mugham, ghazals have also been widely employed in the works of Azerbaijani composers.

The founder of the Azerbaijani professional school of composition, Uzeyir Hajibeyli, succeeded in organically integrating ghazals with professional musical forms and genres in the first opera of not only Azerbaijan but the entire East—the mugham opera *Layla and Majnun* (1908)—as well as in his musical comedies and vocal works. By turning to two ghazals by the

Renaissance poet Nizami Ganjavi and composing *Sensiz* (1941) and *Sevgili Canan* (1943), Hajibeyli created the first examples of the romance-ghazal (tasnif-romance) genre. In these works for voice and piano, the principal features of the romance, the lyrical content of the ghazal, mugham lyricism, ghazal poetic meters, and the logic of mugham development merge into a unified artistic whole.

Azerbaijani composers who skillfully continued Uzeyir Hajibeyli's traditions enriched musical culture with enduring works by turning to the ghazal genre.

The image of Sheikh Nizami Ganjavi and his philosophically profound poetry imbued with boundless love for humanity have been embodied by prominent Azerbaijani composers in various musical genres. Afrasiyab Badalbeyli composed the opera *Nizami*; Niyazi created the opera *Khosrow and Shirin*; Fikret Amirov wrote the *Nizami* Symphony for string orchestra and the *Nizami* ballet; Gara Garayev composed the lyrical choral work *Autumn*, the symphonic poem *Layla and Majnun*, and the ballet *Seven Beauties*; Jahangir Jahangirov composed *Ghazal*; Jovdat Hajiyev wrote the choral works *Ey, Gul*; Soltan Hajibeyov created the children's opera *Iskandar and the Shepherd*; Tofiq Bakikhanov composed the ballet *Good and Evil*; Ramiz Mustafayev wrote the oratorio *Nizami*; and many other composers produced valuable artistic works dedicated to the musical embodiment of Nizami's poetry.

The study, analysis, and broad dissemination of significant findings concerning the embodiment of Nizami's poetry in musical works constitute one of the important tasks facing Azerbaijani musicology. The issues related to the reflection of Nizami Ganjavi's philosophical world in composers' creativity were first examined in the 38-page manuscript *Nizami on Music and in Music*, written in Russian in May 1947 by the prominent Azerbaijani composer and musicologist Afrasiyab Badalbeyli. This work subsequently became a focal point for later generations of musicologists. At

the end of the manuscript, the author discusses compositions created by Azerbaijani composers in various musical genres based on motifs from the great poet's works. Badalbeyli writes: "Attempts to compose musical works related to Nizami's creativity also exist abroad. However, these attempts are very limited and lack boldness. ... Works worthy of the great Nizami, possessing a high artistic level, can be created only in the poet's homeland by the sons of his native land who can deeply feel and profoundly comprehend the essence of his genius" [7, p. 35].

In 1947, on the occasion of the 800th anniversary of the great Azerbaijani poet and thinker Nizami Ganjavi, the prominent Azerbaijani composer Jahangir Jahangirov (1921–1992) composed *Ghazal* for mixed choir and piano to the poet's text—one of the earliest choral works written in this genre. The choral piece was first performed in 1948 by the Azerbaijan State Choral Cappella at the Azerbaijan State Philharmonic named after Muslim Magomayev, and the score was published in 1952 (Baku: Azmusnashr, 1952, 14 pp.). In 2021, the poetic text of the choral work was prepared for publication in Latin script for the first time by the author of the present study; the preface to this edition provides concise information on the composer's creative legacy and the distinctive features of the work [1].

It should be noted that, in addition to composing valuable choral works, Jahangir Jahangirov—who made significant contributions to the development of choral art—worked for many years as the leader of professional choral ensembles and as Head of the Choral Conducting Department at the Azerbaijan State Conservatory, as well as a professor. Through these roles, he carried out sustained and effective activity aimed at the development of choral culture in the country and the training of highly qualified specialists in this field.

While still studying at the Azerbaijan State Conservatory, C. Jahangirov led the choir group of the Azerbaijan State Song and Dance Ensemble founded by U. Hajibeyli. He composed his earliest works specifically for choir and produced choral arrangements of Azerbaijani folk songs. A substantial part of the composer's creative legacy consists of songs and choral works in various genres.

Among Jahangirov's choral compositions are the poem *On the Other Side of the Araz*, the twelve-part composition *Song of Friendship*, choral numbers from the operas *Azad* and *The Fate of the Khananda*, the cantatas *Fuzuli*, *Nasimi*, and *Ashiq Ali*, the oratorio *Sabir*, as well as dozens of choral miniatures.

As a master connoisseur of choral music, Jahangirov employs choral voices in the composition of *Ghazal* for mixed choir and piano, written to the words of Nizami Ganjavi, in full accordance with the principles and laws of choral art. In order to emphasize contrast between sections more clearly, the main thematic material in the outer sections is assigned to the soprano and alto parts. In the contrasting middle section, which represents the climax of *Ghazal*, the leading melodic line is entrusted to the soprano, while the remaining voices (alto, tenor, bass) perform an accompanying function, despite the participation of all voices.

The psychological depth of the work and its international dramaturgy are closely connected with the poetic text. It should be noted that since Nizami's ghazals were written in Persian in accordance with medieval poetic traditions, they were translated into Azerbaijani to reach the modern reader. In this composition, the composer relied on the translation by Jafar Khandan.

The sorrow, melancholy, and emotional tension characteristic of the ghazal genre are vividly reflected in the choral music:

Shall I give my heart again, O faithless and self-centered one,

When you have taken it away, bound to another?

What is this habit of yours, to deem sorrow my rightful share?

That is why among the people I am known as grief-stricken.

I possess no realm like Jamshid's to offer you even a single kiss;

If you consent, I would be torn limb by limb upon the path of love.

Shall I give my heart again, O faithless and self-centered one,

When you have taken it away, bound to another [2].

In accordance with the poetic structure and figurative content of Nizami's ghazal, C. Jahangirov composed his choral ghazal in a three-part form, set in the *Chahargah* mode with a D tonal center. It should be recalled that, in terms of artistic and emotional impact, *Chahargah* evokes feelings of excitement and passion in the listener.

In an article devoted to the composer's oeuvre, the renowned musicologist, Doctor of Art Studies, and Professor Ramiz Zohrabov cites the words of the poet Zeynal Jabbarzadeh, emphasizing Jahangirov's sensitive attitude toward poetry: "He is an artist who hears music within poetry, who can perceive melody in the arrangement and flow of words" [6, p. 33].

In the musical content of Jahangirov's choral ghazal, with the exception of the climactic section, each line of Nizami's ghazal is repeated twice, thereby allowing the musical idea to be conveyed to the listener more fully in close connection with the text.

The work clearly reveals features characteristic of the composer's creative style: fullness of expression; the subtle lyricism of music that follows the literary text; the unity of word and music; a strong connection with the musical heritage of his people; references to national modal systems and mugham sections; and vivid melodicism.

It should be noted that the choral work *Ghazal*, which reflects deep and sincere emotions, was arranged for the balaban instrument by Ilham Najafov, Professor at the Azerbaijan National Conservatory.

Thus, *Ghazal* by the prominent Azerbaijani composer Jahangir Jahangirov, written for mixed choir and piano based on a ghazal by Nizami Ganjavi, is distinguished by its close ties to national traditions and its lyrical qualities, and it opens broad horizons for the use of the ghazal genre in choral art.

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